

Food Micro 2022

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Conference

Next Generation Challenges in Food Microbiology

August
28-31
2022

Megaron Athens
International
Conference Centre
ATHENS, GREECE

Hybrid

Abstract Book

Organized by

International
Committee on
Food Microbiology
and Hygiene

Under the auspices

Hellenic Scientific
Society of
Mikrobiokosmos

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FoodMicro 2022

Next Generation
Challenges in
Food Microbiology

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POSTERS

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Controlling and predicting microorganisms in food ecosystems

P6.78

Effect of lemon balm and spearmint extracts on the survival of *S. aureus* in goat's raw milk cheese

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Previous investigation by our research group has revealed that hydroethanolic solid-liquid extracts from lemon balm and spearmint present high inhibitory capacity against *S. aureus*.

Cheese produced from raw milk has shown moderate prevalence of *S. aureus* in the past, therefore imposing a health safety issue for consumers. Thus, the aim of this study was to evaluate the antimicrobial effect of lemon balm and spearmint extracts against *S. aureus* in goat's raw milk cheeses during maturation.

Lyophilised extracts of lemon balm and spearmint aerial parts were obtained using ethanol 70% (v/v) as solvent in a shaking water bath. Milk was inoculated with *S. aureus* to reach 5 log CFU/g and 1% (w/w) of each extract was added to the curd, while a non-inoculated control was kept. Cheeses were kept in a chamber at 10 °C/98% RH for 15 days. Water activity, pH and *S. aureus* counts were determined at specific days.

For every treatment, a dynamic model was adjusted that consisted of a log-decay function with tail in differential form as primary model (with varying D-value), coupled to a secondary model Bigelow equation of D-value as a function of pH (with parameters log D* at pH 7.0 and zpH).

The dynamic models adequately fitted the survival curves with root mean square errors (RMSE) of 0.1172 and 0.0633, for spearmint and lemon balm, respectively, producing significant parameter estimates. The parameter log D* was affected by the addition of extracts (0.621 [SE=0.061] for spearmint and 1.189 [SE=0.200] for lemon balm) versus the controls (0.932 [SE=0.166] and 0.996 [SE=0.056]); whereas zpH tended to be higher with the addition of extracts (3.172 [SE=0.660] for spearmint and 2.339 [SE=0.835] for lemon balm).

In this sense, the addition of plant extracts significantly decreased the time to achieve one log reduction, which in practical terms corresponded to up to 1.36 log CFU/g reduction by the end of maturation.

Using a dynamic predictive microbiology model, this work characterised *S. aureus* survival parameters in goat's raw milk cheese and demonstrated that lemon balm and spearmint extracts can have a beneficial effect in controlling *S. aureus* during the maturation stage.